

Integrated pest management of hybrid rice to support rice sovereignty program in Yogyakarta

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ABSTRACT

Annual rice consumption always increases as the increase of Indonesian population. Rice is the main food for Indonesian. With rice sovereignty program, Indonesia government is going to target 80.1 million tons of rice production in 2018 through special effort since 2015. Planting hybrid rice is one of some technologies to increase rice production. However, hybrid rice is relatively a new technology that should be scaled up years after and becomes new challenge. Although it has not been largely adopted in Yogyakarta, the assessment of pest and disease on hybrid rice is important, because pest and disease is one major constraint for Yogyakarta rice production, particularly brown plant hoppers and bacterial leaf blight. One cause of brown plant hoppers outbreaks in rice fields is unsynchronized planting of rice crops, susceptible variety, and low management practices. An assessment on the influence of hybrid rice varieties and integrated pest management (IPM) to the abundance of insects and diseases intensity is important. Insect abundance, particularly the varies of natural enemies affected pest control management decision. The research was conducted in Sleman District, Yogyakarta in rainy season of 2017/2018. The objective was to determine the dominant pests and diseases in hybrid rice and to determine the insect abundance as an effect of IPM due to save rice production. Dominant pests found in Yogyakarta hybrid rice are brown plant hopper, stem borer, and leaf folder, while the natural enemies are Coccinelids, Tetragnatha, Micraspis, Cythorinus, Ophionea, and spiders. Bacterial leaf blight and blast were found as the dominant diseases.

Keywords: hybrid rice, insect abundance, pest, disease, natural enemies.

INTRODUCTION

The need of rice as staple food of Indonesian people always increases every year. An increase of Indonesian population results an increase of rice consumption per year. At the same time, fertile rice field areas have been decreased due to land conversion to settlement for the increased population. To overcome this condition, Indonesia government targets 80.1 million tons of rice production in 2018 through special effort named *Upaya Khusus (UPSUS)* since 2015 to meet rice sovereignty program.

Regarding some results of previous studies that grain yield of hybrid rice was at least 10% higher than inbred rice (Zhang et al., 2009; Huang et al., 2010), planting hybrid rice could become one of some technologies to increase high rice production in Indonesia. With average potential yield of hybrid rice that could be over 13 t/ha (Ying et al., 1998; Katsura et al., 2008; Jiang et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2017), production of rice in Indonesia can be estimated doubled.

Although the area of agricultural land has rapidly dedicated to hybrid rice since the late 1970s throughout Asia, particularly in China, India, and Vietnam (Horgan and Crisol, 2013), it is relatively new technology in Indonesia. Hybrid rice begins scaling up years after and becomes new challenge in Indonesia, includes Yogyakarta. Although it has not been largely adopted in Yogyakarta, the assessment of pest and disease on hybrid rice is important, because evidence suggests that hybrid rice is tend to be susceptible against pest damage, such as white-backed planthopper (*Sogatella furcifera*), striped stem borers (*Chilo suppressalis* Walker), yellow stem borer (*Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker), rice leaf folder (*Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*) and the rice skipper (*Parnaraguttatus* Bremer & Grey) (Chieng, 1985; Pang, 1987; Mew et al., 1988; Zhou, 1988; Tian and Li, 1994; Tu et al., 2000; Horgan and Crisol, 2013). Dominant diseases found in hybrid rice are blast and bacterial leaf blight. Rice blast (leaf blast, node blast and panicle blast) is one of the most significant diseases of rice, whereas results to crop failure up to 11% - 30% (Liu et al., 2007; Li and Zhang, 2015). To overcome the blast damage, new resistance hybrid varieties were provided (Xie et al., 2016). On the other side, bacterial leaf blight (BLB) caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *Oryzae* is widely prevalent among various rice varieties and reflected severe yield losses (Arshad et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2015).

In Yogyakarta, pest disease outbreaks in rice fields are caused by unsynchronized planting, susceptible variety, and low management practices. To prevent pest and disease outbreaks, Integrated Pest Management (IPM) was applied in Yogyakarta. IPM has been the dominant crop protection paradigm since the 1960s. In IPM, farmers are practicing to make decisions about managing pest that are knowledge-based and economically justified, to minimize the risks on environment and human health (Parsa et al., 2014). IPM in Yogyakarta consists of pest and disease monitoring twice a month, application of *Beauveria bassiana* as biological control agent, and the use of Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) as resistance inducer. Many research reported that significant insect pest problems can be prevented by abundant natural enemies in tropical Asian irrigated rice (Matteson, 2000). Studies of food web (Heong et al., 1991; Heong et al., 1992; Inthavong et al., 1998; Roger et al., 1998; Schoenly et al., 1996, 1998) and studies of the biology, ecology, and impact of

predator and parasitoid (de Kraker, 1996; Kamal et al., 1990; Vromant et al., 1998) have emphasized the biodiversity of rice fauna, including the richness of natural enemy. Complex and rich web of generalist and specialist predators and parasites controlled rice pests. If undisturbed, these natural enemies normally prevent significant insect pest problems (Barrion and Litsinger, 1995; Okuma, 1993; Shepard et al., 1987, 1995; van Vreden, 1986). The objectives of this research is to determine the IPM effect to the intensity of pest disease and to determine the abundance of insects in hybrid rice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted at Seyegan, Sleman District, Yogyakarta in rainy season of 2017/2018. This area was recorded as high rice damaged caused by stemborer, plant hopper, and bacterial leaf blight (BTPP DIY, 2017). It has sandy loam soil, located at 165 m above sea level with air temperature 24° C – 29.4° C, air humidity 70% – 95%, average atmosphere level 976.9 – 1004.7 mbar, wind velocity 2-20 m/s, rainfall 135 mm, and raindays 12-26 times (BPS Sleman, 2017).

This research was designed in randomized completely block with three replications as on farm research. Ten varieties of hybrid rice and one inbred rice (IR-64) were planted on the rice field owned by farmers. IPM was developed through: 1) pest and disease monitoring twice a month, 2) application of *Beauveria bassiana* at seedling stage, vegetative stages (30 DAP), generative stage (40 and 55 DAP) as biological control agent, and 3) the use of Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) as resistance inducer at 55 DAP.

Thirty plants which systematically random selected was observed for disease intensity and pest damage recording. Disease intensity of blast and bacterial leaf blight, also pest damage intensity of brown plant hopper and leaf folder was assessed by a standard method of the Direktorat Perlindungan Tanaman Pangan (2018), as follow:

$$I = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^z (n_i \times v_i)}{Z \times N} \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

- I = damage intensity or disease intensity (%)
- ni = number of infected or damaged plants with scale of damage
- vi = scale of damage
- N = total numbers of plants assessed
- Z = highest scale of damage

Damage intensity of stem borer was assessed by a by a standard method of the Direktorat PerlindunganTanaman Pangan (2018) as mentioned below.

$$I = \frac{n}{N} \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

- I = damage intensity (%)
- n = number of damaged plants
- N = total numbers of plants assessed

Population of pest and natural enemies was observed from 10 net swing sweeping. Wide swing coverage was 100 cm, with 40 cm distance among swing rows (Direktorat Perlindungan Tanaman Pangan, 2018). The observation on pest population, disease intensity, and natural enemies abundance was conducted once a week at 38th – 59th days after planting. Collected data was analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistic 20 and further analyzed using Duncan’s 5%.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Hybrid rice is still not largely adopted in Yogyakarta. Some farmers and agriculture technical office are questioning and concern in the possibility of pest and disease outbreak regarding the unknown resistance or susceptibility of new hybrid rice varieties against pest and diseases. Since rainy season 2017/2018, ten new hybrid rice varieties were introduced to farmers. Preventing pest and disease outbreak, IPM was applied. Besides synchronous planting and new varieties that were expected more tolerant to pest disease, *Beauveria bassiana* was applied four times. Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) was also applied at 55 DAP to suppress disease intensity of bacterial leaf blight and blast as well as promote plant growth (van Loon, 2007). The bacterial genera such as *Agrobacterium*, *Arthrobacter*, *Azotobacter*, *Azospirillum*, *Bacillus*, *Burkholderia*, *Caulobacter*, *Chromobacterium*, *Erwinia*, *Flavobacterium*, *Micrococcous*, *Pseudomonas*, *Serratia*, *Allorhizobium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Mesorhizobium* and *Rhizobium*, belongs to PGPR (Ahemad and Kibret 2014; Gupta *et al.*, 2015). The effect of this IPM approach to pest population, the abundance of natural enemies, and disease intensity was assessed with this following results.

Pest population and intensity of crop damage at ten hybrid rice varieties and one inbred variety with IPM application

Leaf folder, brown plant hopper and stem borer were dominant pest that were found in this research during 38th – 59th days after planting. This research showed that population of each pest were same or less than 3 (three)

based on 10 swing net sweeping (Table 1). However, the damage of rice caused by these pests were nothing. The highest crop damage was 13.3%, found at HIPA Jatim2 Pertani hybrid variety, caused by leaf folder at the 45th days after planting (Table 2). Based on the observation, crop damage caused by leaf folder was higher than stem borer and brown plant hopper. Moreover, crop damage by brown plant hopper was not found because the population of this pest was very low to cause crop damage.

Table 1. Population of Leaf folder (imago phase), brown plant hopper, and stem borer (imago phase) at the 38th – 59th days after planting

Variety	Crop damage by Leaf folder at days after planting				Crop damage by Brown plant hopper at days after planting				Crop damage by Stem Borer at days after planting			
	38 th	45 th	52 nd	59 th	38 th	45 th	52 nd	59 th	38 th	45 th	52 nd	59 th
Pertiwi	1	0	0	2 ^{ab}	0	0 ^b	0	0	0	0	0	0
SL8	1	0	0	0 ^b	0	0 ^b	1	0	0	0	1	0
Mapan P05	0	0	0	0 ^b	0	1 ^{ab}	0	0	0	0	0	0
HIPAA8	0	0	0	3 ^a	0	0 ^b	0	0	0	0	0	1
HIPAA9	0	1	0	0 ^b	0	2 ^a	0	0	0	1	0	0
HIPAA18	1	0	1	0 ^b	0	0 ^b	0	0	1	0	0	0
HIPAA19	0	0	1	3 ^a	0	0 ^b	0	0	0	0	1	0
HIPAAJatim2	0	0	0	0 ^b	0	0 ^b	0	0	0	0	0	0
Petro												
HIPAA18	0	0	0	3 ^a	0	0 ^b	1	0	0	0	0	0
HIPAA												
Jatim2												
Pertani	1	1	0	0 ^b	0	0 ^b	0	0	0	0	0	0
IR64	0	0	1	0 ^b	0	1 ^{ab}	0	0	0	0	1	0

Values with the same letter at the same column is not significantly different according to Duncan's 5% test

Table 2. Damage Intensity of Rice Crop caused by Leaf folder, brown plant hopper, and stem borer at the 38th – 59th days after planting

Variety	Crop damage by Leaf folder at days after planting				Crop damage by Brown plant hopper at days after planting				Crop damage by Stem Borer at days after planting			
	38 th	45 th	52 nd	59 th	38 th	45 th	52 nd	59 th	38 th	45 th	52 nd	59 th
Pertiwi	6.7 ^a	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^{ab}	6.7 ^b	0.0	0.0 ^b	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a
SL8	10.0 ^a	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^{ab}	0.0 ^c	0.0	0.0 ^b	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a
Mapan P05	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^c	0.0	3.3 ^a	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a
HIPA8	3.3 ^{ab}	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^{ab}	6.7 ^b	0.0	3.3 ^a	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a
HIPA9	0.0 ^b	10.0 ^b	3.3 ^{ab}	0.0 ^c	0.0	0.0 ^b	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a
HIPA18	6.7 ^a	3.3 ^b	6.7 ^a	0.0 ^c	0.0	3.3 ^a	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a
HIPA19	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	6.7 ^a	10.0 ^a	0.0	0.0 ^b	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a
HIPAJatim2	3.3 ^{ab}	0.0 ^a	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^c	0.0	3.3 ^a	0.0	0.0	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b
Petro	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	6.7 ^a	10.0 ^a	0.0	3.3 ^a	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	0.0 ^b
HIPA18	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	6.7 ^a	10.0 ^a	0.0	3.3 ^a	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	0.0 ^b
HIPA Jatim2	6.7 ^a	13.3 ^a	6.7 ^a	0.0 ^c	0.0	3.3 ^a	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a
Pertani	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	6.7 ^a	0.0 ^c	0.0	3.3 ^a	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	0.0 ^b
IR64	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	6.7 ^a	0.0 ^c	0.0	3.3 ^a	0.0	0.0	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	0.0 ^b

Values with the same letter at the same column is not significantly different according to Duncan's 5% test

This result indicates that IPM and the application of *B. bassiana* at seedling stage, vegetative stages (30 DAP), and generative stage (40 and 55 DAP) worked good to control leaf folder, brown plant hopper and stem borer. It was reported that fungi *B. bassiana* (Hypocreales: Cordycipitaceae) is a prominent agent and have broad spectrum for insect biological control (Herlinda *et al.*, 2006; Rachmawaty *et al.*, 2016). The density of *B. bassiana* spores used in this research was 6.05 × 10⁸ spores/ml, obtained from BPTP DIY laboratory.

Disease Intensity at ten hybrid rice varieties and one inbred variety with IPM application

Based on the observation of disease during 38th – 59th days after planting (DAP), bacterial leaf blight and blast were the dominant disease. The result showed that disease intensity of bacterial leaf blight was 0 – 6.7%, while blast was 0 – 13.3% (Table 3). As an increase of crop age, disease intensity of these diseases were also increased. It seems that once the pathogen infected rice crop, it resulted symptoms that could not be able to be reduced, but it succeed to be suppressed by the application of IPM, particularly the use of non - pathogenic bacteria belongs to plant growth promoting rhizobacteria.

Table 3. Disease intensity of bacterial leaf blight and blast at the 38th – 59th days after planting

Variety	Bacterial leaf blight				Blast			
	38 th	45 th	52 nd	59 th	38 th	45 th	52 nd	59 th
Pertiwi	0.0 ^b	6.7 ^a	3.3 ^{ab}	3.3 ^a	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b
SL8	3.3 ^a	6.7 ^a	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^a	6.7 ^a	6.7 ^a	13.3 ^a
Mapan P05	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^{ab}	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b
HIPA8	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^{ab}	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b
HIPA9	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	6.7 ^a	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	6.7 ^a	6.7 ^a	10.0 ^a
HIPA18	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^{ab}	6.7 ^a	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b
HIPA19	0.0 ^b	6.7 ^a	3.3 ^{ab}	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	6.7 ^a	6.7 ^a	6.7 ^{ab}
HIPAJatim2	3.3 ^a	6.7 ^a	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b
PetroHIPA18	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^{ab}	6.7 ^a	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b
HIPAJatim2Pertani	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^b	6.7 ^a	3.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	6.7 ^a	6.7 ^a	10.0 ^a
IR64	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^{ab}	6.7 ^a	3.3 ^a	0.0 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b	3.3 ^b

Values with the same letter at the same column is not significantly different according to Duncan's 5% test

Insect abundance as the effect of IPM at ten hybrid rice varieties and one inbred variety

Pest and natural enemies were observed at the 38th – 59th days after planting. Result shows that population of pest at different hybrid varieties and inbred varieties was lower than the population of natural enemies. Six pest species found in this research were leaf folder, stem borer, brown plant hopper, rice bug, and white-backed plant hopper, while eight species of natural enemies found were spiders, odonata, coccinelids, tetragnatha, ophionea, cythorinus, micraspis, and conocephalus. Pest population outbreak was not found from daily insects observation. Pest population seems to be well controlled as the effect of IPM with an average as 23 pest at the 38th days, 26 pest at the 45th days, 34 pest at the 52nd days, and 29 pest at the 59th days. From the aspect of natural enemies population, it always seemed to be higher than pest population, as 57 pest at the 38th days, 49 pest at the 45th days, 67 pest at the 52nd days, and 70 pest at the 59th days. It is assumed that IPM, which means low synthetic chemical pesticide input affected high and balance abundance of insects (pest and natural enemies). This result is in line with the findings that brown plant hopper outbreaks was occurred in linked with high pesticide input (Gallagher et al., 1994; Heinrichs, 1994; Bottrell and Schoenly, 2012). Moreover, concerning worries of pest outbreaks due to the inherited susceptibility of hybrid varieties (Cheng, 2009; Horgan et al., 2016), this research proved that IPM can be a good way to control pest population in Yogyakarta hybrid rice.

Table 4. Population of pest and natural enemies at the 38th – 59th days after planting

Variety	38 th		45 th		52 nd		59 th	
	Pest	Natural enemy						
Pertiwi	2 ^a	6 ^{ab}	2 ^b	8 ^{ab}	4 ^{ab}	5 ^b	3 ^a	6 ^b
SL8	2 ^a	6 ^{ab}	1 ^b	3 ^c	1 ^b	2 ^b	2 ^a	6 ^b
Mapan P05	1 ^{ab}	8 ^{ab}	1 ^b	7 ^{ab}	3 ^{ab}	5 ^b	2 ^a	5 ^b
HIPA8	1 ^{ab}	2 ^b	2 ^b	2 ^c	5 ^a	5 ^b	3 ^a	5 ^b
HIPA9	3 ^a	7 ^{ab}	1 ^b	6 ^{ab}	1 ^b	5 ^b	2 ^a	7 ^b
HIPA18	4 ^a	16 ^a	7 ^a	11 ^a	6 ^a	20 ^a	3 ^a	18 ^a
HIPA19	0 ^b	4 ^b	3 ^b	4 ^{bc}	4 ^{ab}	5 ^b	3 ^a	5 ^b
HIPA Jatim2	3 ^a	1 ^b	1 ^b	1 ^c	2 ^b	6 ^b	2 ^a	5 ^b
Petro HIPA18	2 ^a	1 ^b	3 ^b	1 ^c	4 ^{ab}	7 ^b	3 ^a	5 ^b
HIPAJatim2Pertani	2 ^a	1 ^b	1 ^b	2 ^c	1 ^b	2 ^b	2 ^a	2 ^b
IR64	3 ^a	5 ^{ab}	4 ^{ab}	4 ^{bc}	3 ^{ab}	5 ^b	4 ^a	6 ^b
Total	23	57	26	49	34	67	29	70

Values with the same letter at the same column is not significantly different according to Duncan's 5% test

Yield of ten hybrid rice varieties and one inbred variety as an effect of IPM

Rice yield was measured by 2.5 m x 2.5 m of crop cut at harvested stage of each hybrid and inbred variety. With low pest population, low disease intensity and good abundance of natural enemy as IPM result, rice yield of ten hybrid rice varieties and one inbred variety is mentioned in Table 5.

Table 5. Yield of ten hybrid rice varieties and one inbreed variety

Variety	Yield (ton/ha)
Pertiwi	8.6
SL8	6.3
MAPAN P05	8.5
HIPA8	7.4
HIPA9	6.5
HIPA18	5.9
HIPA19	6.0
HIPA JATIM2	7.5
Petro HIPA18	7.6
HIPA Jatim2 Pertani	7.8
IR64	6.1

CONCLUSION

1. Dominant pests found in Yogyakarta hybrid rice are leaf folder, brown plant hopper, and stem borer, while bacterial leaf blight and blast were found as the dominant disease.
2. IPM provided high abundance of natural enemies such as *coccinelids*, *tetragnatha*, *micraspis*, *cythorinus*, *ophionea*, and spiders that were believed as the control agents in food web balance and suppress the population increase of dominant pests.
3. Implementation of IPM such as tolerant varieties, synchronous planting, biological control agents, and periodically pest disease monitoring could maintain low population of pest and low diseases intensity in an area planted with hybrid rice.

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